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EDITORIAL NOTE

It is with great pride and enthusiasm that we present the maiden edition of the *Gamji Journal of Arts and Humanities*, published by the Gamji Institute for Training and Research. This inaugural publication marks a significant milestone in our commitment to fostering academic excellence and contributing to the scholarly discourse in various fields of study.

The articles featured in this edition represent a diverse range of research topics, each offering valuable insights and advancing our understanding of critical issues. The depth and breadth of the studies reflect the dedication and scholarly rigor of the authors, and we are honored to showcase their work.

We extend our heartfelt gratitude to the authors for their invaluable contributions and to the peer reviewers for their diligent efforts in ensuring the quality and integrity of the research presented. We also express our appreciation to the editorial board and support staff whose dedication and hard work have made this publication possible.

As we embark on this scholarly journey, we invite readers to engage with the research presented in this journal, to reflect on the insights offered, and to contribute to the ongoing dialogue in their respective fields. We look forward to future editions and the continued growth of the *Gamji Journal of Arts and Humanities* as a platform for academic excellence and intellectual exchange.

Sincerely,

Prof. Aminu Ahmad
Chairman, Editorial Board
Gamji Journal of Arts and Humanities
Gamji Institute for Training and Research

EFFECT OF TECHNOLOGICAL FACTORS ON INTENTION TO ADOPT INDUSTRY 4.0 TECHNOLOGY: THE ROLE OF TOP MANAGEMENT SUPPORT

By

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ABSTRACT

The General objectives of these research work is to assess the “Effects of Technological Factors on Intention to Adopt Industry 4.0 Technology: The Role of Top Management Support.” The increasing use of technology by firms has necessitated the need to further understand the factors that influence the rate of technology adoption by Small and Medium Enterprises SMEs in Nigeria, specifically amongst printing press SMEs in Bauchi State. Unified Theory of Acceptance and Use of Technology (UTAUT) was used as the underpinning theory in this research work. Related literatures by various authors on Industry 4.0 Technology were reviewed, survey research method was adopted in the research work. Three research questions, developed into seven research hypotheses, guided the study. A structured questionnaire was used for data collection and the population for the study is 274 printing press employees in Bauchi metropolis. The Data collected was analysed using Smart PLS SEM 4.0 and SPSS 20. The study finds that, perceived relative advantage and perceived compatibility are positively and significantly associated with SME's intention to adopt industry 4.0 technology. It was concluded that in order to remain competitive, it is important for printing SMEs to stay up to date with the latest trends in printing technology and techniques. Among the recommendation was that Printing SMEs should endeavour to adopt the use of industry 4.0 technology facilities so as to maintain high standards of quality to effectively satisfy the need of their customers.

Keywords: Intention, adoption, Industry 4.0, Technology, SMEs.

1. INTRODUCTION

The increasing use of technology by firms has necessitated the need to further understand the factors that influence the rate of technology adoption by Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs) in Nigeria, specifically amongst printing press SMEs in Bauchi State. Developments in technology have resulted in the wide penetration of its use in different areas of business, including SMEs. Adamu (2019) stated that SMEs are globally recognised as catalysts of economic growth and development; providing opportunities that create jobs and income re-distribution within economies.

As technology keeps advancing at an accelerated rate, small and medium sized enterprises (hereafter SMEs) must prepare to adapt to the emergence of technology under an uncertain economic realm. Growing evidence shows Industry 4.0 technology has brought massive opportunities in respective industries, manufacturing and information technology. Innovation capability has become a distinct possibility, set to serve better product and service reengineering and distinction, (Muhamad, Syed Mohamad and Nor, 2021).

Industry 4.0 technology, known as the fourth technological transformation towards digital-physical systems in manufacturing, creates a disruptive impact on industries. Manufacturing companies, especially small and medium-sized ones, are facing various challenges and must constantly innovate to remain competitive. Traditional SMEs like printing press SMEs in developing countries cannot move abruptly to an integrated production and management system. Thus, it is necessary to establish an industrial implementation strategy for this type of companies (Akintayo, Akinlabi, Okokpujie, Ishola, & Akinlabi, 2021).

Adoption of Industry 4.0 technology causes a firm to improve its business procedures and diminishing expenses. Nigerian manufacturing SMEs are still at a low-level stage since a significant number of its administrators are as yet to utilize the conventional based methodologies as opposed to embracing current advances. However, the out-of-date advanced technology executed cannot meet the conception and administration difficulties, (Vision 20:20 Technical Report on SMEs, 2009 in Akinlabi, Babaremu, Okokpujie, & Akinlabi, 2019).

Large corporations and smaller high-tech companies are already investing in the perceived opportunities and benefits of the Industry 4.0 technology, while small and medium-sized companies (SMEs) do generally not possess the resources or competence required to join the race. The degree to which enterprises are equipped to face Industry 4.0 technology differs vastly between the larger ones and the SMEs due to distinctions in financial and technical resources as well as experience with regards to management of new technologies (Stentoft, Jensen, Philipsen & Haug, 2019).

The subsequent inequality in resources significantly impacts the industry as a whole, as witnessed by the reduction in the number of small-scale printing firms that cannot compete with the larger firms that can cost-effectively and quickly print the same products with better quality (Muhammad, Siti, & Ruslan, 2019).

The adoption of Industry 4.0 technology and the utilization of information and communication technology is expected to have several positive impacts on SME development and competitiveness. Despite these benefits, Industry 4.0 technology has not yet gained sufficient trust of SME management due to the gap between financial constraints and creative amenities. (Mirwan, et al., 2021).

Small and Medium-sized Enterprises (SMEs) face the hurdle of possessing neither human nor financial resources to systematically investigate the potentials and risks of introducing Industry 4.0 technology. (Dominik, Vladimir, & Helmut, 2020). SMEs are struggling with the process of adopting Industry 4.0 technology due to insufficient resources (Muller, 2019) and are hardly growing; instead, they are trying to survive with financial deficit (Wei & Talib, 2019).

Despite abundant studies exploring Industry 4.0 application on SMEs, efforts to explore their intention to adopt industry 4.0 technology in the context of Nigeria SMEs and Bauchi state SMEs in particular, are still insufficient. Therefore, this study is important as it fills the gap by assessing the “Effects of Technological Factors on Intention to Adopt Industry 4.0 Technology: The Role of Top Management Support.”

Figure 1: Research framework

2. HYPOTHESIS DEVELOPMENT

The study of the “Effects of Technological Factors on Intention to Adopt Industry 4.0 Technology: The Role of Top Management Support” will be developed and hypothesized based on the above construct in the research framework:

2.1 PERCEIVED RELATIVE ADVANTAGE OF INDUSTRY 4.0 TECHNOLOGY

The phrase ‘relative advantage’ refers to the advantage one gets by using latest technology as opposed to previous ones. What innovation is sought depends on what the user wants to improve. Innovations whose advantages are very clear, such as strategic effectiveness (e.g., increasing sales) and operational effectiveness (e.g., reducing costs) are more likely to be adopted. Industry 4.0 technologies have so far shown that they can considerably improve processes and practices, so they have a good chance of being adopted. Relative advantage has been found to play an important role in technology diffusion so this concept must be studied ever more in the context of Industry 4.0 (Jayashree et. al., 2021). Relative advantage is the degree of additional benefit for the organization from adopting the innovation compared to the status quo. A recent study by Commerzbank (2019), on

the impact of the digital trend on manufacturing firms revealed that firms tend to accelerate ICT integration to establish new business models and innovations to counter the competitive pressure and short product life cycles. Therefore, advanced manufacturing is expected to be able to give organizations a better competitive advantage (Martin Prause, 2019). However, the introduction of technologies and concepts inherited from the Industry 4.0 paradigm is considered strategic also for small and medium sized enterprises (SME) to ensure competitiveness, increasing productivity and flexibility of production systems, while matching the growing market demand for customised products and services (Riccardo et al., 2020). Several scholars agreed that Industry 4.0 technology can provide, beyond economic advantages, numerous opportunities for environmental and social sustainability. The main advantages linked to the adoption of Industry 4.0 concern the possibility of increasing the quality of products through the reduction of errors. Advantages in the management of logistics and time saving are also considered major benefits following the implementation of Industry 4.0 concepts (Riccardo et al., 2020).

Considering all the review on relative advantage and similar study above, this study therefore posits that relative advantage is a main factor that can persuade companies to adopt Industry 4.0 technologies, because companies adopt technologies whose benefits clearly outweigh any downsides.

Hypothesis one (H₁): Perceived relative advantage is positively associated with SME's intention to adopt industry 4.0 technologies.

2.2 PERCEIVED COMPATIBILITY OF INDUSTRY 4.0 TECHNOLOGY

The issue of the importance of compatibility has come up in several studies. How much a new technology is compatible with existing company structures, infrastructure, procedures and values influences its likelihood of being adopted. The most ideal situation is when new technologies are compatible with current technological infrastructure and work practices. For SMEs, to avoid resistance from employees, it is important that changes are compatible with their culture. E-businesses are technological by nature, so they have a good starting point, but they still need to find systems compatible with their organization. Old production systems and work practices can greatly hinder the adoption

of Industry 4.0 technologies. Without proper compatibility, there is a real risk of adoption failure (Jayashree et. al., 2021).

When starting the project of adoption and implementation of an Industry type concept 4.0, it is necessary to analyze the compatibility between the existing process and the one that is intended to be installed in terms of automation, collection and transmission of information. Thus, the PLC responsible for the drive and control of the cutting process needs to be compatible with the entire control system installed, and have the necessary communication port for network communication. In fact, real-time communication through IoT is one of the pillars of the implementation of any evolution system for Industry 4.0 (Pinto, Silva, Costa, Campilho and Pereira, 2019).

In the age of Industry 4.0 technology, relevant data transparency is required across the supply chain, whereas existing systems might not be easily compatible, and adjustment to technological advancement is risky and absorbs a lot of financial resources (Vytautas et al., 2020). Old equipments are primarily a problem from the production and economic point of view for a given enterprise. Old machines often break down, require a great deal of repairs, are not very efficient and often cause incompatibilities from the point of view of employees and are also dangerous to use. This affects the costs of the enterprise's operation, especially the cost of repairs and thus result in high prices of the sold products. Moreover, old equipments also have a greater impact on the natural environment surrounding such enterprises, increasing waste and emissions to the atmosphere (Manuela et al., 2019).

Thus, this study concludes that if SMEs have negative feelings towards advanced technologies, they will find their adoption hard to master. If, however, Industry 4.0 is concomitant with the technology that companies already use, then its technologies will more likely be successful in SMEs. Based on findings from past studies, the following hypothesis was proposed:

Hypothesis Two (H₂): Perceived compatibility is positively associated with SMEs intention to adopt industry 4.0 technologies.

2.3 PERCEIVED COMPLEXITY OF INDUSTRY 4.0 TECHNOLOGY

Complexity is the degree to which the technologies are perceived as challenging to understand and use, and it is typically negatively correlated with adoption (Premkumar and Roberts, in Martin Prause, 2019). The lack of knowledge is the second major obstacle for Industry 4.0 adoption for SMEs (Wischmann, Wangler, and Botthof, 2019).

Technologies are considered to be more complex. The more challenging they are to use; The higher the level of complexity, the less they are likely to be adopted (Jayashree et. al., 2021). Lack of technical expertise often hinders SMEs from adopting Industry 4.0 technologies because of their complexity (MITI, 2019). Complexity is usually measured by looking at the number of diverse relationships and the number of diverse elements. Cyber-physical systems have multiple heterogeneous specialized devices which are able to operate flexibly according to the environment they are in. They do this with the help of data analysis and applications which integrate different business functions and innovations (Martin 2019). However, for such a system to work smoothly, there should ideally be a set of protocols and communication standards that make integration across business functions easier. Making hardware and software run smoothly together can be particularly complex (Raj, Dwivedi, Sharma, De-Sousa Jabbour and Rajak, 2020). When there is a lot of complexity, users often feel confused and are not sure about how to use the technology. This can negatively affect the decision to adopt new technology (Mark. 2015 in Jayashree et. al., 2021). Studies in the past have identified a strong correlation between functionality and the decision to adopt new technologies (Alalwan, Dwivedi, and Rana, 2021; and Jayashree et. al., 2021). Attitudes of individuals towards technology are usually based on the perception of complexity (Dwivedi, Rana, Jeyaraj, Clement, and Williams, 2019). For example, blockchain technology is often perceived as complex by individuals and so they find it difficult to understand and have confidence in it unless it is integrated in easier-to-use systems (Wong, Leong, Hew, Tan, and Ooi, 2020). The transaction mechanisms of blockchain have raised concerns about their speed. Furthermore, blockchain implementation can partly be hindered by security challenges or the fact that the technology is still in its infant stage (Saber et al., (2019). When users feel that they don't have much control over the outcome of a system, they become increasingly suspicious about that system; From companies' point of view, they will be less likely to adopt a new technology if they see it as very complex and incompatible with

their present technologies and practices (Rana, Dwivedi, Williams, and Weerakkody, 2016 in Jayashree et. al., 2021).

From these literature support, hypothesis three is proposed:

Hypothesis Three (H₃): Perceived complexity is positively associated with SMEs intention to adopt industry 4.0 technologies.

2.4 TOP MANAGEMENT SUPPORT ON INDUSTRY 4.0 TECHNOLOGY

Exploiting the potential of Industry 4.0 technology is challenging, particularly for Small and Medium-sized Enterprises (SMEs), as it requires significant investments in technologies. However, this is not enough because because IT competences, a strategic vision of the top management and an organizational context ready to support the transformation process and receive the benefits led by these technologies need to be considered (Lara and Anna, 2019).

Top Management is in charge of providing the company's future direction, nurturing its values and beliefs, and giving the firm a sense of identity. Not only do managers spearhead the company, but they also guide employees' behavior. Past research has proved that top management support is fundamental in the adoption of the new technologies for the success of the innovative projects and in the integration of technologies into business processes, which in turn facilitates the adoption and usage of cloud computing tools (Lara et al., 2019).

Top Management championship is an important factor for assimilating information technologies, such as Web technologies, because it defines institutional norms and values and how the company perceives the innovation. If the top management believes in the innovation and actively shapes the vision and strategy, this serves as a strong signal to the organization to overcome obstacles in the assimilation process. The significance of top management beliefs and active participation has been demonstrated in various studies. Thus, top management support is positively related to adoption. This is supported by Wischmann, Wangler and Botthof (2019) who highlighted that the lack of a digital vision by the top management is an inhibitor to the implementation of Industry 4.0.

SMEs have a very vertical organisation with a concentration of power in the hands of the manager. The hierarchical line is short, and the leader is deeply involved in the daily life of the company. Experts note that the leader's attitude towards Industry 4.0 technology is key for an SME to adopt this concept. Experts specify that a manager with a strongly operational presence can balance resources to enable the realisation of an Industry 4.0 project. In the case of a manager with an 'early adopter' profile, he will seek to quickly implement Industry 4.0 technology or any other technology that he thinks could have a positive impact on industrial performance. Conversely, a leader with a 'conservative' profile will be more reluctant to adopt such concepts and technology (Alexandre, Samir, Robert, Simon, Estefania and Romain, 2020).

Top management knowledge of technology's benefits and enterprise's expectations as well as concomitant support are critical adoption predictors. Top management commitment/support is the involvement, enthusiasm, motivation, and encouragement by management towards the acceptance of information system innovations and a stronger involvement in technology adoption and usage. Top management plays crucial role in influencing other organizational members to accept ICT; furthermore, they also commit resources to its adoption. Technology acceptance and use may not be considered a priority when management do not see the benefits derived from such technology (Igwe, Ebenuwa, and Idenedo, 2020). On the strength of the above literature, the following hypothesis was proposed:

Hypothesis Four (H₄): Top management support is positively associated with SMEs intention to adopt industry 4.0 technologies.

2.5 MEDIATING EFFECT OF TOP MANAGEMENT SUPPORT (TMS)

The mediating effect of TMS is described as a situation where TMS entirely or partially mops up the effects of technological factors on intention to adopt Industry 4.0 technology (Cepada-Carrión, Nitzl, Roldán, 2018 in Jayeola, Sidek, Abdul-Samad, Hasbullah, Anwar, An, Nga, Al-Kasasbeh, Ray, 2022). Because top management plays such a crucial role in organizational performance, SMEs, whose owners are often also managers, require a strong TMS in the successful adoption of Industry 4.0 technology if they are to gain the economic benefits of the technology. The role of top management has always been to

support employees, assist them with solving problems, foster amicable interactions and coexistence between various job functions, encourage bottom-up innovativeness and incentives, and guide managers to advocate IT innovation by transmitting clear and unwavering messages that lay a clear foundation (Jayeola et al., 2022). CEOs and other members of top management must first understand the benefits of innovation, such as Industry 4.0 (Cloud Computing), and how they contribute to the company acquiring a competitive edge and enhancing its performance. As a result, top management will be urged to devote all necessary resources in adopting Industry 4.0 Technology successfully and increasing its use, which will improve the organization's performance (Jayeola et al., 2022). Organizations having TMS demonstrated improved operational, strategic, and administrative performance as a result of top management's role in encouraging active participation and securing necessary resources throughout this stage. Top management has a big impact on how effectively cloud technology is used for better organizational performance, as it allocates resources, integrates services, and re-engineers business processes. Khayer, Talukder, Bao and Hossain (2020) showed that the performance of Bangladeshi SMEs improved when top management allotted significant resources and became involved in the whole process of Industry 4.0 (cloud computing) diffusion. By delivering rewards/incentives to improve user motivation and by changing performance targets, top management operates as a mechanism for improving firm performance through the use of IT (Jayeola et al., 2022). The foregoing discussion indicates that the presence of TMS on the successful adoption of Industry 4.0 Technology is a precursor to the realization of full business benefits.

Muhamad et al., 2021; Alshamaila & Papagiannidis, 2013; Borgman, Bahli, Heier & Schewski., 2013; Low, Chen & Wu., 2011; Ifinedo, 2011; Tornatzky & Fleischer, 1990) held that the acceptance of technological adoption in an organisation will be much easier when it receives full support and devotion provided by top management and that, since top management acts as the decision maker, their decision affects the technology adoption process.

Therefore, the following hypothesis were proposed:

Hypothesis Five (H₅): Top management support has mediating effect on perceived cost and SMEs intention to adopt industry 4.0 technologies.

Hypothesis Six (H₆): Top management support has mediating effect on perceived relative advantage and SMEs intention to adopt industry 4.0 technologies.

Hypothesis Seven (H₇): Top management support has mediating effect on perceived compatibility and SMEs intention to adopt industry 4.0 technologies.

3. METHODOLOGY

A survey design was adopted in carrying out this research. The population for this study is 274 employees of Printing Press SMEs in Bauchi metropolis. These figures were obtained from the Printing Press Association of Bauchi State. Based on the basis of the rule of thumb that "the larger the sample size the better the result", this present study added 30% of the 161 minimum sample size obtained using raosoft online calculator. Therefore the sample for this study became 209. The sampling technique this study employed is simple random sampling technique where each sampling unit within a population has an equal chance of being selected for the sample.

The instrument for data collection was a structured questionnaire which was subjected to face and content validation by the researcher's supervisor and other experts in the field of Management Science from Bauchi State University, Gadau. The study applied reliability analysis to assess internal consistency of the study variables. Cronbach's Alpha coefficient was computed on all components of questionnaire and their assessment given. Alpha of 0.7 and above was used in this study as a threshold.

The data collected from the respondents based on the questionnaire distributed to them was analysed using Smart PLS SEM 4.0 and Statistical Package for Social Science (SPSS 20). Firstly, an Exploratory Data Analysis (EDA) using SPSS was conducted to test the normality, outliers and clean the data from errors. Also, descriptive analysis was conducted using SPSS 20 to assess the frequency distribution and percent of the demographic profile of the respondents such as gender, age groups, educational level, years of working experience and rank. The second aspect of the data analysis for the research deals with assessing measurement and structural model. At this point, the reliability and validity of the measurement model was established using the Smart PLS Version 4.0.

4. DESCRIPTIVE STATISTICS OF QUESTIONNAIRE ITEMS AND CONSTRUCTS

Table 1 below shows the mean and standard deviation values for all the 25 items and 5 constructs used in this study. The descriptive statistics for items on the 5-Likert scale show that PRA4 and PCX3 has the highest mean value of 4.06, while PRA1 has the lowest mean value of 3.75. Similarly, for standard deviation, IA4 has the highest value of 0.909, and PCT4 with the lowest value of 0.721. Table 4.3 provides the detailed statistics for each respective item and construct of the study.

Table 1: Descriptive Statistics for Items and Constructs

(N=200)	Items	Mean	Std. Deviation
Perceived			
Relative			
Advantage			
PRA1	Reduce the cost of operations.	3.75	0.895
PRA2	Increase resource efficiency.	3.91	0.807

PRA3	Improve material usage.	3.84	0.831
PRA4	Produce customized products.	4.06	0.754
PRA5	Increase sales and revenue.	3.77	0.819

Perceived

Compatibility

PCT1	Fit our printing business well to adopt.	4.00	0.737
PCT2	Requires few firm-specific adaptations.	4.03	0.801
PCT3	We can integrate the software easily into our existing IT setting.	3.90	0.783
PCT4	Compatible with the existing values of our employees.	3.85	0.721
PCT5	Compatible with the mentality of our employees.	3.97	0.769

Perceived

complexity

PCX1	Our employees have knowledge and understanding of industry 4.0 technology.	3.87	0.785
PCX2	Our employees do not require a lot of training to adopt industry 4.0 technology.	4.02	0.802

PCX3	We have the technical support required to implement Industry 4.0 technology.	4.06	0.754
PCX4	We have adequate infrastructural systems to implement industry 4.0 technology.	3.97	0.758
PCX5	Skills required to use industry 4.0 Technologies are too complex for our employees.	3.89	0.775
Management support			
MS1	The top management is likely to be interested in adopting industry 4.0 technology.	3.90	0.827
MS2	The top management is likely to invest funds for industry 4.0 technology	3.85	0.773
MS3	The top management is willing to take risks in the adoption process of industry 4.0 Technology.	3.98	0.753
MS4	The top management is likely to consider the adoption of industry 4.0 technology as strategically important.	3.91	0.831
MS5	The top management has articulated a vision or strategy for the organizational use of industry 4.0 technology.	3.85	0.779

Intention to
adopt

IA1	Actions to adopt Industry 4.0 technology fully in the medium term is in place.	3.99	0.757
IA2	Managers tend to adopt new technological products before other people.	4.03	0.801
IA3	The trustfulness of the cloud storage provider is a crucial factor within the adoption decision process.	3.97	0.736
IA4	Technological infrastructure to support the processes is important	3.78	0.909
IA5	Financial limitations and cost reduction are	3.97	0.739

considered by the organization.

4.1 ASSESSMENT OF MEASUREMENT MODEL

Smart PLS 4.0 by (Ringle, Wende, & Becker, 2015) was fully utilized in running the regression analysis for the research model. Hair et al. (2017, 2014) suggested that dual stages are involved in examining a model using PLS-SEM. The first stage deals with the measurement model assessment, while the second stage comprises structural model assessment.

Figure 1: Measurement Model

Convergent Validity

The convergent validity assessment of the measurement model, AVE was also assessed. The AVE stands as the squared loadings' grand mean of all items related to a construct (Hair et al., 2017). To attain convergent validity, the AVE value for each construct must be above 0.50 (50%) (Hair, Hult, Ringle, & Sarstedt, 2014; Hair et al., 2017).

Table 4.5 indicates that the AVE values were within the range of 0.500 and 0.643, this is above the rules of thumb. Hence, with item loadings above 0.50, CR that is above 0.70, and AVE also above the threshold of 0.50, the measurement model of this study has adequately met the required standard. Therefore, the model has established suitable convergent validity. Figure: 3 also shows the result of the measurement model assessment.

Table 2: Convergent Validity of Measurement Model

Construct	Item	Loadings	CA	CR	AVE
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Perceived relative advantage	PRA1	0.758	0.853	0.895	0.631
	PRA2	0.807			
	PRA3	0.842			
	PRA4	0.747			
	PRA5	0.812			
Perceived compatibility	PCT1	0.813	0.758	0.832	0.500
	PCT2	0.719			
	PCT3	0.638			
	PCT4	0.691			
	PCT5	0.663			
Perceived complexity	PCX1	0.788	0.861	0.900	0.643
	PCX2	0.811			
	PCX3	0.779			
	PCX4	0.803			
	PCX5	0.825			
Management support	MS1	0.732	0.843	0.888	0.613

	MS2	0.788			
	MS3	0.815			
	MS4	0.787			
	MS5	0.791			
Intention to Adopt	IA1	0.829	0.777	0.842	0.518
	IA2	0.717			
	IA3	0.655			
	IA4	0.668			
	IA5	0.716			

Table 3: Heterotrait-Monotrait (HTMT) Matrix

Construct	IA	MS	PCT	PCX	PRA
IA	0.000				
MS	0.780	0.000			
PCT	0.643	0.804	0.000		

PCX	0.638	0.578	0.751	0.000
PRA	0.788	0.442	0.806	0.790 0.000

4.2 ASSESSMENT OF STRUCTURAL MODEL

The structural model aimed at confirming the research model empirically. It is the stage where some fundamental analyses such as collinearity assessment, assessing the significance of the path coefficients, the coefficient of determination (R^2) values, the effect size (f^2) as well as the predictive relevance (Q^2) and PLSpredict (Q^2 predict) are performed. The hypotheses and mediation relationships were also tested and confirmed here in the structural model using the bootstrapping process.

Table Error! No text of specified style in document.: Coefficient of Determination (R^2)

Constructs	R^2 value	Interpretation
Intention to adopt	0.948	Substantial
Management support	0.866	Substantial

Hair et al. (2011): (R^2) values of 0.25, 0.50 and 0.75 as weak, moderate and substantial, respectively.

Table 5: Predictive Relevance (Q^2)

Endogenous Constructs	Q^2 Value	Predictive Relevance
Intention to adopt	0.112	Yes

Management support	0.107	Yes
Perceived compatibility	0.125	Yes
Perceived complexity	0.164	Yes
Perceived relative advantage	0.103	Yes

Table 6: Effect Sizes (f^2)

Construct	Effect Sizes (f^2)	Interpretation
IA		
MS	0.001	Small effect
PCT	0.747	Large effect
PCX	0.004	Small effect
PRA	0.018	Large effect

Kenney's (2018) thresholds of 0.005, 0.01, and 0.025 for small, medium, and large respectively.

Importance-Performance Matrix Analysis (IPMA)

Figure 2: Importance Performance Map

4.3 DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

This present study was designed to assess the “Effects of Technological Factors on Intention to Adopt Industry 4.0 Technology: The Role of Top Management Support.” The study was able to achieve several outcomes with the help of data analysis. The finding of each hypothesis will be discussed and will be complemented by prior studies.

H₁: Perceived relative advantage is positively associated with SMEs intention to adopt industry 4.0 technologies.

The first alternative hypothesis of the study postulates that “Perceived relative advantage is positively associated with SMEs intention to adopt industry 4.0 technologies.” (H₁). This relationship is supported, as the path coefficient for this relationship shows a statistically positive and significant result with ($\beta = 0.065$, $t\text{-value} = 2.318$ and $p < 0.010$). This very finding of (H₁) was also empirically complemented by prior studies. Several scholars statistically agree that Industry 4.0 technology can provide, beyond economic advantages, numerous opportunities for environmental and social sustainability.

Riccardo et al., (2020) statistically assert that, the main advantages linked to the adoption of Industry 4.0 concern the possibility of increasing the quality of products through the reduction of errors. Advantages in the management of logistics and time saving are also considered major benefits following the adoption of Industry 4.0 concepts.

Jayashree et. al., (2021) in their study revealed that relative advantage has been positively and significantly found to play an important role in technology diffusion. Innovations whose advantages are very clear, such as strategic effectiveness (e.g., increasing sales) and operational effectiveness (e.g., reducing costs) are more likely to be adopted. Bai, Dallasega, Orzes and Sarkis (2020) found that among the litany of benefits, Industry 4.0 technology can provide manufacturing firms with profitable business models, higher efficiency, quality, and improved workplace conditions. Vytautas, Valentinas, Katarína, Małgorzata and Waldemar, (2020) statistically assert that, Industry 4.0 technology gives the industry a new perspective that allows it to work with new technologies to achieve maximum efficiency with the minimal use of resources in the manufacturing industry.

H₂: Perceived compatibility is positively associated with SMEs intention to adopt industry 4.0 technologies.

Similarly, the second alternate hypothesis (H₂), which postulates that “Perceived compatibility is positively associated with SMEs intention to adopt industry 4.0 technologies” was also supported. This is so because the path coefficient for this relationship turns out to be statistically positive and significant with ($\beta = 0.876$, t-value = 5.973 and $p < 0.000$). Empirically, the study of Usman, Ahmad, and Zakaria, (2019) also confirmed the positive relationship between compatibility and the adoption of new technologies. Xuan and Quang, (2020) statistically affirmed that adoption of compatible Industry 4.0 technologies will have a significant impact of the product design and development process. From a planning perspective, technologies can provide an integration of comprehensive and timely updated product data that allow design managers to develop and optimize project plans.

Furthermore, Martin Prause, (2019) asserted that higher technological compatibility of the innovation with the existing system implies higher adoption capability of the organization; Old production systems are strong inhibitors to adopt Industry 4.0

technology. A study by Kurnia, Choudrie, Mahbubur, and Alzougool, (2015) in Jayashree et. al., (2021) concluded that the higher the level of perceived structure compatibility, the more likely it was that advanced technologies would be adopted. An empirical study by Arnold, Veile, and Voigt, (2018) in Jayashree et. al., (2021) reached a similar conclusion about Malaysian manufacturing SMEs. The study claimed that compatibility leaves a positive impact and persuades employees to take up the use of a new technology. When the new processes fit with the old system, companies are more likely to implement a new value creation approach.

H₃: Perceived complexity is positively associated with SMEs intention to adopt industry 4.0 technologies.

The third alternate hypothesis (H₃), which postulates that “Perceived complexity is positively associated with SMEs intention to adopt industry 4.0 technologies” is not supported as the path coefficient that specified this relationship was statistically positive but insignificant with ($\beta = 0.054$, $t\text{-value} = 0.950$ and $p < 0.171$). Empirically, the finding of this hypothesis is in line with Martin (2019), who asserted that complexity is the degree to which the technologies are perceived as challenging to understand and use, and it is typically negatively correlated with adoption. Wischmann, Wangler, and Botthof (2019) found that lack of knowledge is the major obstacle for the adoption of Industry 4.0 by SMEs. Lai-Wan, Lai-Ying, Jun-Jie, Garry, & Keng-Boon (2019), statistically found that a high degree of complexity confuses users and causes them to have difficulty in understanding and using a technology, which in turn adversely impacts its adoption decision.

Also, Jayashree et. al., (2021) statistically affirm that technologies are considered to be more complex. The more challenging they are to use; the higher the level of complexity, and the less they are likely to be adopted. MITI (2019) found that lack of technical expertise often hinders SMEs from adopting Industry 4.0 technologies because of their complexity. Mark (2015) in Jayashree et. al., (2021) statistically opined that when there is a lot of complexity, users often feel confused and are not sure about how to use the technology. This can negatively affect the decision to adopt new technology. Rana, Dwivedi, Williams, and Weerakkody, (2016) in Jayashree et. al., (2021) complemented that when users feel that they don't have much control over the outcome of a system, they

become increasingly suspicious about that system. From companies' point of view, they will be less likely to adopt a new technology if they see it as very complex and incompatible with their present technologies and practices.

H₄: Management support is positively associated with SMEs intention to adopt industry 4.0 technologies.

The coefficient of the interaction term of management support and SMEs intention to adopt industry 4.0 technology is positive but statistically insignificant with ($\beta = 0.007$, t-value = 0.154 and $p < 0.439$). This result did not provide support for the fourth hypothesis (H₄), which states that "Management support is positively associated with SMEs intention to adopt industry 4.0 technologies." Empirically, the result for this (H₄) is in line with the findings of Arnold, Veile & Voigt (2021) who asserted that support and assistance from top management is a crucial aspect if an organisation aims to adopt industry 4.0 effectively, as its execution involves wide-scale investments. Along with that, Rajnai & Kocsis (2021) pointed out that although some business managers are perceptive and mindful of the presence of Industry 4.0, yet they are apprehensive as their companies are unequivocally unprepared for the full implementation of it.

H₅: Management support has mediating effect on perceived relative advantage and SMEs intention to adopt industry 4.0 technologies.

For H₅, the results show that the mediating role of management support on perceived relative advantage and intention to adopt is positive but not significant with ($\beta = 0.000$, t-value = 0.064, and $p < 0.475$). This result did not provide support for the fifth hypothesis (H₅), which states that "Management support has mediating effect on perceived relative advantage and SMEs intention to adopt industry 4.0 technologies." Empirically, this is in line with the finding of Jayeola et al., (2022) who asserted that CEOs and other members of top management must first understand the benefits of innovation, such as Industry 4.0 (Cloud Computing), and how they contribute to the company acquiring a competitive edge and enhancing its performance. As a result, top management will be urged to devote all necessary resources in adopting Industry 4.0 Technology successfully and increasing its use, which will improve their organization's performance.

H₆: Management support has mediating effect on perceived compatibility and SMEs intention to adopt industry 4.0 technologies.

Similarly, the results for (H₆) also show that that the mediating role of management support on perceived compatibility and intention to adopt is positive but not significant and does not provide support for the sixth hypothesis (H₆) which postulated that “Management support has mediating effect on perceived compatibility and SMEs intention to adopt industry 4.0 technologies” with ($\beta = 0.000$, $t\text{-value} = 0.099$, and $p < 0.461$). Empirically, this is in line with Cepada-Carrión, Nitzl, Roldán, (2018) in Jayeola, Sidek, Abdul-Samad, Hasbullah, Anwar, An, Nga, Al-Kasasbeh, Ray, (2022) who affirmed that mediating effect of TMS is described as a situation where TMS entirely or partially mops up the effects of technological factors on intention to adopt Industry 4.0 technology. SMEs, whose owners are often also managers, require a strong TMS in the successful adoption of compatible Industry 4.0 technology if they are to gain the economic benefits of the technology.

H₇: Management support has mediating effect on perceived complexity and SMEs intention to adopt industry 4.0 technologies.

Lastly, with ($\beta = 0.006$, $t\text{-value} = 0.155$, and $p < 0.439$), the results for (H₇) also shows that that the mediating role of management support on perceived complexity and intention to adopt is positive but not significant and does not provide support for the seventh hypothesis (H₇) which postulated that “Management support has mediating effect on perceived complexity and SMEs intention to adopt industry 4.0 technologies.” Empirically, this is in line with the findings of Muhamad et al., 2021; Alshamaila & Papagiannidis, 2013; Borgman, Bahli, Heier & Schewski., 2013; Low, Chen & Wu., 2011; Ifinedo, 2011; Tornatzky & Fleischer, 1990) that the acceptance of technological adoption in an organisation will be much easier when it receives full support and devotion from top management and that, since the top management acts as the decision makers, their decision affects the technology adoption process.

5. CONCLUSION

Printing in Nigeria is a growing industry that is becoming increasingly more important to the Nigerian economy. It is a sector that provides vital services to businesses and individuals, allowing them to create a wide range of printed materials. The sector includes a range of services such as digital printing, offset printing, and screen printing. These services can be used to create variety of products such as books, magazines, flyers, brochures, and posters. Printing in Nigeria also offers a range of binding services, including perfect binding, saddle stitching, and case binding.

The industry is becoming ever more competitive as more businesses and individuals seek out printing services in Nigeria. In order to remain competitive, it is important for printing SMEs to stay up to date with the latest trends in printing technology and techniques. In addition, it is important for SMEs to maintain high standards of quality, as this will help to ensure that their customers are satisfied with the results.

5.1 RESEARCH IMPLICATION

This study has implications for SMEs that feel threatened by the emergence of Industry 4.0 and related technologies. The study shows that SMEs intention about these technologies is crucial to respond to external changes and to understand the benefits of such technologies. This means that managers in SMEs have to train their production staff and product engineers in these methods to enable employees to assess such technologies and evaluate which ones are promising and which ones are not. Without such intention, companies are likely to reject new technologies since they cannot understand their potential and benefits.

This also has implications for policy makers aiming to speed up the diffusion of Industry 4.0 technologies. They should try to facilitate knowledge transfer between those entities that know Industry 4.0 technologies (technology producers or universities) and SMEs. Furthermore, implementing a new technology is not only about the technology itself. Bundled regulations create barriers for SMEs to adopt the new technology. A clear framework that could guide the company through the journey of adoption would be very helpful for SMEs.

Theoretically, this study added to the existing body of knowledge; Most of the previous research on industry 4.0 was done using direct relationship. This study combined perceived relative advantage, perceived compatibility and perceived complexity in a single study and introduced management support as mediating variable to explain this research work on “Effect of Technological Factors on Intention to Adopt Industry 4.0 Technology: The Role of Top Management Support.”

5.2. SUGGESTIONS FOR FURTHER RESEARCH

This study also has limitations, which indicate directions for future research. Since this topic is within manufacturing SMEs, it is a quite new phenomenon, there were some constraints regarding previous studies and academic journals that had focused on Nigerian SMEs and their intention for Industry 4.0. The scope for this study was limited to printing press SMEs, which may limit its generalisability to other manufacturing SMEs and service oriented SMEs. The researcher is therefore suggesting that future studies should be carried out in order to test the generalizability of the study findings. Also, future studies should adopt the use of moderators on this topic. This study is also suggesting that future study on this topic should be conducted on service industry.

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